

Numerical modelling of porosity formation in thermoplastic composites undergoing thermal decomposition at high temperatures

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Context and objectives

- Study the resistance to fire of aeronautical composite structural parts [1,2]
- Experimental investigation of C/PPS laminates thermal decomposition through time and for different temperatures (up to 600°C)
- Create a meso-structure based FE model of the laminates:
 - Identify and quantify the porosity formation
 - Explicitly represent the transformation of matrix elements into porosities
- Model the influence of porosity formation on the thermo-mechanical behavior under thermal aggression (high temperature or flame exposure)

Typical porosity gas pocket in the thermal decomposition regime

Experimental setup

- Thermal decomposition of samples under isothermal conditions (furnace)
- Geometry and mass measurements to determine the porosity content
- Optical microscopy / X-ray tomography to evaluate the space distribution of porosities

Thermally decomposed samples at 530°C during 7 minutes: (a) optical microscopy, (b) X-Ray tomography

Numerical setup

- Explicit yarn/matrix representation FE model
- 1/28th of RVE (1.7x1.03x2.2mm³)
- 5,000,000 elements
- Thermo-mechanical properties (yarn & matrix) from [3]
- QI: quasi-isotropic lay-up

Experimental results and identification of the model

- 3 porosity formation mechanisms:
 - ① • Nucleation → probabilistic law $p(t,T,\Delta t)$ governing the porosity formation
 - ② • Growth / coalescence → impact of local porosity volume fraction on $p(t,T,\Delta t)$
 - ③ • Yarn / matrix interface decohesion
- Significant porosity-induced swelling: ① & ② → internal pressure within the porosities
③ → cohesive elements (work in progress)
- Porosity formation at the end of each time increment Δt
- Structural damage to yarn integrity for $t > 5\text{min}$ and $T > 500^\circ\text{C}$ → modelling limitations

Nucleation kinetics model

The porosity volume fraction η_p solution of the differential equation:

$$\dot{\eta}_p(t, T) = G(t, T) (1 - \eta_p(t, T)) \quad \text{where} \quad G(t, T) = \frac{p(t, T, \Delta t)}{\Delta t} \quad \xrightarrow{\text{closed form}} \quad \eta_p(k\Delta t) = \sum_{i=1}^k (-1)^{i+1} \sum_{c \in C_{i,k}} \prod_{j \in c} p_j \quad \text{with } C_{i,k} \text{ the set of possible combinations of } i \text{ elements out of } k$$

Parameter identification

$$G(t, T) = \frac{\tau_1 + \tau_2 \left(\frac{T - T_d}{T_{ref} - T_d} \right)^b}{t + \tau_3} \quad + \quad \text{Identification using Euler's scheme and optimization}$$

Parameter	Unit	Value	Main role
τ_1	No unit	0.205	Affects G for $T = T_d$
τ_2	No unit	0.139	Dependance of G to T
τ_3	Time (s)	15.0	Time shift at the initial time
b	No unit	1.15	Dependence of $\frac{\partial G}{\partial T}$ to T
T_{ref}	°C	530.0	Intermediate temperature

Coupled flame / mechanical modelling

- Heat flux imposed on the upper surface
- Radiation and convection on the back

Example of a 116kW/m² heat flux

Example after 90s: swollen laminates / thermal decomposition state

Axial stress distribution

Conclusions and perspectives

- ✓ Numerical modelling of the time and temperature influence on the porosity content, the nucleation and growth mechanisms and the induced swelling
- ✓ The model has been used to predict the porosity distribution resulting from a thermal aggression and to simulate the loading capabilities of the decomposed sample
- Interface decohesion consideration through cohesive elements will be pursued
- Further characterization of the mechanical behavior will be carried out and compared with numerical results to study the thermomechanical coupling

References:

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- [3] Y. Carpier, B. Vieille, F. Barbe, and A. Coppalle. "Meso-structure-based thermomechanical modelling of thermoplastic-based laminates subjected to combined mechanical loading and severe thermal gradients". *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 162, pp. 107–165, 2022.